

Australasian Computational and Simulation Commons (ACSC)

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP723
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - June 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	University of Queensland
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	Curtin University Australian National University University of Wollongong Monash University University of Melbourne University of Technology Sydney Griffith University Latrobe University Adelaide University
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Alan Mark

1.1 Background

The aim of the project is to consolidate, store and distribute high-value data derived from Quantum Mechanical (QM) calculations and atomic level computer simulations of molecular systems. Data derived from QM calculations on individual molecules together with computer simulations of the dynamic behaviour of complex molecular systems play a central role in drug development, the design of novel materials and work to understanding the function of cellular components. For example, in the recent COVID pandemic QM calculations and atomic simulations facilitated the rapid development of targeted anti-viral agents.

Such calculations represent very large investments of time and computing resources and as such the results of these calculations, in some cases accumulated over decades, have long-term value. Despite this, there is no central local where such data can be deposited. Instead, computational data is generally held by individual groups or organizations. It is fragmented, often difficult to find and not readily accessed by others. Given its ongoing utility and the magnitude of the investment associated with its creation, this data needs to be centralized, organized and shared.

The consolidation of computational data on molecule systems within Australia will facilitate the development and validation of methodology, aid the interpretation of experimental data, and provide a starting point for future research.

The ACSC was built using two existing data assets: the Automated Topology Builder (ATB) molecular repository (atb.uq.edu.au) and the ATB simulation repository (molecular-dynamics.atb.uq.edu.au). These repositories were already well established and operated at scale. The ATB had operated for over a decade and contained data on hundreds of thousands of compounds with thousands of registered users from across the world. The more recently established simulation repository contained the output of simulations of over a thousand systems representing tens of millions of hours on national high-performance computers.

The project itself was focused on extending these existing platforms to enable data from groups across Australia to be incorporated. As part of this program, community archiving standards were established and automated search and curation tools implemented. The ultimate goal of the project was to consolidate both existing and newly generated data in order to open new avenues of research and ensure high level computational data is accessible to all.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

Aim 1: To store and distribute high-value data derived from QM calculations.

The outputs from QM calculations are an integral component of the ATB repository, a community driven initiative in which academics and students in Australia and across the globe can submit molecules of interest to obtain structural and energetic information and be parameterized for use in simulations. At the start of the project the ATB repository contained data on ~ 450,000 compounds with ~ 13,000 registered users. Over the course of the project this has expanded to > 900,000 compounds and > 20,000 registered users making it now one of the largest molecular databases of its type in the world. A key element of this was the developed of tools to import data from multiple sources and to serve heats of formation for a given molecule at multiple levels of theory. For example, Dr Lars Goerigk (UMelb) is one of the lead developers of the GMTKN55 database of QM data related to main-group elements. This includes thermochemistry and related data for over 3,000 compounds calculated at multiple levels of theory. ATB entries for all molecules within the GMTKN55 database were created and compatible data from GMTKN55 incorporated.

Aim 2: To consolidate and make publicly available key simulation data from partner organizations.

Simulations of the dynamic behaviour of complex molecular systems play a central role in areas ranging from drug and materials design to understanding the function of cellular components. We have developed a framework consolidating simulation data including establishing hierarchal criteria for data inclusion and retention, parsers for metadata extraction, tools for validation of data from different sources, tools to allow approved users to annotate specific data sets, and tools to enable data to be automatically grouped based on metadata. We have also developed a downloadable tool that users can

use locally to organize and validate their data before upload. User data is displayed using the latest version of the open source CKAN frontend.

Aim 3. Development and implementation of automated curation tools (metadata extraction, searching and classification tools).

The ability to extract metadata and to automatically curate entries within the ATB and simulation databases is key to maintaining consistency within the data as well as enhancing searchability, usability and in general improving the utility of stored data. As part of this new molecular classification tools were implemented to identify chiral centres, as well as to identify, generate and link alternative protomeric forms of molecules (tautomeric forms involving the movement of hydrogens). The use of graph-based approaches to recognize equivalent sub-structures in different molecules was also expanded. This is important in applications such as drug design where users may wish to search for all molecules that contain a given active sub-structure. It is also used to match terms such as dihedral angles.

Aim 4: Update and improved interoperability of platforms for both data providers and users.

Increased modularization of existing platforms and components with a move toward containerization where possible to reduce hardware dependencies. The ATB front end was adapted to display data for multiple levels of theory for a given molecule. Operability features, such as expected wait times for operations to be completed, have been added. The molecular database links to internally alternative protomeric forms of a given molecule and externally when one or more of those forms are found in external databases such as the ChEMBL database. Access control and account management has been simplified by the implementation of AAF sign in for the simulation repository.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
WP1 – Standards for the generation, collection and storage of QM and simulation (meta)-data		
Initial guidelines for incorporation of new data	Guidelines evolved as trial data was assembled. Initial guidelines were formalized when external data began being incorporated	31/01/2022
Final guidelines for incorporation of	Guidelines for inclusion and curation of simulation data have been posted on the simulation repository site. Guidelines for submission	30/06/2023

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
new data and curation of old data	of molecules to the ATB are incorporated into general usage conditions.	
WP2 – Development and implementation of automated curation tools		
Molecular Metadata (tautomers)	Tautomers have been integrated into the ATB database. A publication is in the draft stage.	20/12/2021
Molecular Metadata (chirality, dihedrals)	Chirality data is now displayed. A graph-based system for defining dihedral archetypes and matches has been developed with empirical assignments being progressively phased out. A description of these components will be included in the next ATB release and publication.	31/10/2022
Parsers for specific data formats	Parsers to import structural data from different sources for processing by the ATB have been developed.	30/06/2023
Automation of curation of old data	Criteria for automatic curation have been developed and the data structured so that persistent data (needed for regeneration) is separated from non-essential data. Currently, a point where data curation rules would be enforced (storage limitations, minimal retention times, low access criteria) has not been reached. Rules will be applied progressively as the need arises.	30/06/2023
WP3 – Interoperability of existing platforms		
FAIR(A): Permissions management and verification system for simulation repository	Single-sign-on using the AAF Rapid Connect service has been implemented. Permissions for access to datasets can now be linked explicitly to AAF identities as required. This feature is now fully developed pending only a swap of our live and development sites to be available to users.	31/4/2023
FAIR(F): Generation and assignment of DOIs &/or other recognised referencing elements. Links to external databases	DOIs have been assigned to databases. Extensive discussions with ARDC and UQ about minting DOIs for specific data sets. Machinery is in place to generate DOIs automatically. Need solution regarding which organization would be responsible for DOIs minted for individual datasets.	30/08/2022

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
APIs for data submission, searching and extraction	The ATB and CKAN interfaces both have extensive APIs implemented. For example, the ATBs API supports: submission of new molecules, searching with metadata and 3D geometry, and the download of output files. Users must request API access which is granted if the use is appropriate.	01/07/2021
WP4 – Consolidation of existing data sourced from project partners		
Incorporation of trajectories generated using GROMOS, GROMACS, AMBER	These parsers are fully functioning.	30/06/2022
Incorporation of trajectories generated using LAMMPS, NAMD and CHARMM	Development of parsers for these codes has been delayed but is expected to be completed shortly.	30/06/2023
Incorporation of molecules and QM data in the GMTKN55 database	The data has been parsed and incorporated into a secondary ATB database.	01/05/2022
Incorporation of other QM data	Tools to incorporate a variety of QM data have been implemented. Groups are being progressively invited to upload data.	30/06/2023
WP5 – Updated web interfaces		
Incorporation of new functionality into existing platforms to improve user experience	A range of new functionality has been incorporated including: new search facilities, new metadata, improved ability to cross reference data.	31/12/2022
WP6 – Modularisation of existing platforms and components		

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
Separation of databases into units that can be made platform independent	A containerised version of the ATB has been developed, tested and distributed to collaborators and commercial customers.	31/12/2022
Impact/Outcome Monitoring Systems (Implementation Work Package)		
Implement the Counter Code of Practice for Research Data in Repositories	Internal usage tracking statistics implemented but these are not yet in a COUNTER-compliant format that can be connected to a usage statistics service.	30/06/2023
Embed Data Metrics Badge on repository landing page	The DataCite metrics badge has been implemented, but currently has limited functionality.	20/01/2022
Link the repository to the IRUS-ANZ - CAVAL (or similar repository)	As the COUNTER code of practice has not yet been implemented fully (output format), we are currently unable to link the repository to a service that relies on COUNTER-compliant usage statistics.	30/06/2023
Implement user discussion group using an open-source platform	User discussion groups have been implemented using Discourse in combination with Discourse Single Sign On and AAF Single Sign On. The end result is that users can access both the simulation repository and Discourse using their AAF credentials. We have configured CKAN to have Discourse embeds on all dataset pages and automatically create topics for each dataset. This feature is now fully developed pending only a swap of our live and development sites to be available to users.	30/05/2023
Conduct online stakeholder survey	This will be conducted once all consortium members have had the opportunity provided data to simulation repository.	30/06/2023

2.2 Project outputs

The Automated topology Builder (ATB) and Repository (<https://atb.uq.edu.au>): The ATB is a web accessible tool that provides atomic interaction parameters and a range of calculated properties of chemical compounds. The data provided by the ATB is used in a wide range of applications including structure-based drug design, materials engineering and biomolecular structure refinement. The ATB provides force field parameters in formats compatible with GROMACS, GROMOS and LAMMPS simulation packages and CNS, Phenix, CCP4, Refmac5 and CYANA X-ray and NMR refinement packages. The ATB also acts as a repository for the results from Quantum Mechanical calculations including optimized geometries, heats of formation, partial atomic charges and electrostatic potential energy surfaces. Incorporated within the ATB are also a range of molecule search and classification tools that allow users to match molecules from partial information, identify common substructures, assign chirality and identify tautomeric forms of a given molecules (molecular forms that can interconvert spontaneously). A key feature of the repository is that it is community driven with registered researchers and students able to submit molecules of interest to be processed. In addition, pre-calculated data can be incorporated and made publicly available. As of May 2023, the site held data on over 890,000 molecules with over 20,000 registered users world-wide.

ACSC Simulation Repository (<https://scmb-ckan.research.dc.uq.edu.au/>): The ACSC simulation repository is a web accessible repository that consolidates, stores and distributes high value data derived from computer simulations of the dynamic behaviour of complex molecular systems in areas ranging from drug and materials design to understanding the function of cellular components. Australian researchers deposit pre-validated data onto a central server from where the data is extracted, parsed to extract meta-data and automatically incorporated into the online repository. Datasets can be tagged according to the submitting group, the system simulated and a range of other qualifiers. The data can also be search based on the system force field, or specific parameters. Data is accepted in a range of formats including GROMOS, GROMACS and AMBER with validation tools and parsers for other major codes including LAMMPS, NAMD and CHARMM being developed. Uses with AAF login credentials can annotate entries. In addition to archiving important results, the repository will greatly facilitate new avenues of research. The repository provides reference data, equilibrated starting structures for new studies, allows the results of previous studied to be re-analysed using new techniques will enable large-scale comparisons to be made between studies (e.g. meta-studies of force field effects). While individual groups and organization have in the past made simulation data available the ACSC repository is the first national repository of its type. A similar endeavour was recently initiated in the European Union opening opportunities for national repositories to be linked further advancing their utility.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
Training on use of the ATB	CHEM3011 Physical Chemistry: Modelling Molecular Behaviour	28	Sept 2021
Training on use of the ATB	CHEM3011 Physical Chemistry: Modelling Molecular Behaviour	25	Sept 2022
Presentations by Dr Sharif Nada and Dr Martin Stroet	CTCMS Symposium on Computational Methods and Applications	50	13-14/3/2023
Presentation by Dr Sharif Nada	Queensland Research Software Developers Forum	50	18/5/2023

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

Molecule Repository: The ATB repository has been in operation since 2011. It is community driven and has over 20,000 registered users. The ATB is also used in teaching and research across the globe. The incorporation of the ATB into the ACSC, the use of the site to consolidate data from multiple sources within the Australian research community and the addition of new frameworks to generate and display metadata have only increased to long term viability of the site. The number of new registered users per year continues to increase with the number of downloads per month increasing by 30% over the last year. ATB development has been primarily funded via grants from the ARC. It is currently funded till the end of 2024. From 2024 to 2030 development of the ATB is expected to continue as part of the Centre of Excellence in Quantum Biotechnology currently being established. A condition of using of the ATB is that users must be based at academic (or not for profit) research organization and that all molecules submitted are be made publicly accessible (non-commercial use). There are also ongoing efforts to commercialise aspects of the ATB via UNIQUEST the commercialization arm of UQ. A containerized version of the public site (without accompanying data) has been licenced to several large chemical and

pharmaceutical companies. This allows companies to generate a molecular database inhouse. As the functionality and usability of the ATB is increased its commercial value will increase. The aim of partial commercialization is to enable the public ATB site to be fully self-sustaining.

Simulation repository: The simulation repository on which the ACSC was initially established in 2018 primarily as an internal group data repository and as a way to distribute data to external users. It was publicly accessible but not publicised. Nevertheless, the repository attracted the attention from multiple groups both in Australia and overseas with several people requesting if their data could be included. We note that a similar project with funding of Euro 3.3 million has recently been established to cover the EU affiliated countries. There is clearly strong demand from within the computational community. While the utility is obvious the diverse nature of the data, the need for data to be repeatedly parsed and curated to maintain relevance and the volume of data make the both the establishment and maintenance of a simulation database challenging. Indeed, in the longer term it is inappropriate for the responsibility to fall on either a single group or university. During its initial establishment phase as a public resource (the next 2-3 years) can be part of the Centre of Excellence in Quantum Biotechnology. However, it is expected the repository will grow rapidly into a national resource. When this occurs, ongoing infrastructure and financial support would be required. At this time it would be appropriate for one of the national computing centres to assume responsibility for the repository as part of their core business.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	DOIs generated for the ATB and simulation repository, internal unique identifiers used for the ATB (molecule id) and simulation repository (dataset id, internal) in lieu of the ability to mint DOIs for individual outputs.
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Achieved
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	Records exist for both the ATB and simulation repository
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they	N/A

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
	exist)	
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	Internally assigned persistent identifiers already exist for both repositories. Individual data output DOIs have not yet been implemented.
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	Achieved
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	Achieved
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	Achieved
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	Achieved
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	Not yet achieved
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	Achieved
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	True for ATB. Not yet on simulation repository as still looking to use DOIs for individual data sets. Machinery in place which will be activated depending on the persistent identifier chosen.
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	Achieved

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	Achieved
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	Lack of community consensus or existing vocabularies, data models, and ontologies. Ongoing efforts to set up a similar repository to the simulation repository in the EU may lead to the development of this consensus over time.
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	This is being currently implemented on the simulation repository.
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	Achieved
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	This is available on some but not all. It is being propagated throughout.
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	This is in place for the ATB. A publication is being prepared to which a citation will be added.
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	Achieved
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	Achieved

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
ATB Github	<p>The ATB github has 28 repositories which proved access to various parts of the project developed as part of the ACSC.</p> <p>Where possible ATB support tools made fully public.</p>	https://github.com/ATB-UQ
ATB Frequently asked questions	User feedback has been consolidated into frequently asked questions.	https://atb.uq.edu.au/index.py?tab=faq
Online resources produced by others.	A number of groups and organizations have developed online resources that build on the ATB.	https://github.com/simongravelle/atb2lamps https://uniquet.com.au/available_technology/automated-topology-builder/ https://www.lammps.org/prepost.html#atb https://www.moltemplate.org/ https://www.academia.edu/28611290/An_Automated_Force_Field_Topology_Builder_ATB_and_Repository_Version_1_0 https://gromacs.bioexcel.eu/t/atb-server/753 https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:62d1f81

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
Research Articles	Articles describing functionality in the ATB have been cited over 2000 times.	<p>Malde AK, Zuo L, Breeze M, Stroet M, Poger D, Nair PC, Oostenbrink C, Mark AE. <i>An Automated force field Topology Builder (ATB) and repository: version 1.0</i>. J. Chem. Theory Comput., 2011, 7, 4026-4037. DOI:10.1021/ct200196m</p> <p>Validation</p> <p>Stroet M, Caron B, Visscher K, Geerke D, Malde AK, Mark AE. <i>Automated Topology Builder version 3.0: Prediction of solvation free enthalpies in water and hexane</i>. J. Chem. Theory Comput. 2018, 14, 11, 5834-5845 DOI:10.1021/acs.jctc.8b00768</p> <p>Koziara KB, Stroet M, Malde AK, Mark AE. <i>Testing and validation of the Automated Topology Builder (ATB) version 2.0: prediction of hydration free enthalpies</i>. J. Comput. Aided. Mol. Des., 2014, 28, 221-233. DOI:10.1007/s10822-014-9713-7</p>
Research Articles	Work associated with the ACSC project. Made possible using tools and new capabilities stemming from the project or reference data in the simulation repository.	<p>Kuschert S, Stroet M, Chin YKY, Conibear AC, Jia X, Lee T, Bartling CRO, Stromgaard K, Guntert P, Rosengren KJ, Mark AE, Mobli M. <i>Facilitating the structural characterisation of non-canonical amino acids in biomolecular NMR</i>. Magnetic Resonance, 2023, 4, 57-72. DOI:doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000602558</p> <p>Stroet, M, Caron, B, Engler, MS, van der Woning, J Kauffmann, A, van Dijk, M, El-Kebir, M, Visscher, KM, Holownia, J, Macfarlane, C, Bennion, BJ, Gelpi-Dominguez, S, Lightstone, FC, van der Storm, T, Geerke, DP, Mark, AE, and Klau, GW <i>OFraMP: A Fragment-Based Tool to Facilitate the Parametrization of Large Molecules J.</i></p>

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
		<p><i>Computer Aided Molecular Design. 2023: In press.</i></p> <p>Zhou, Z, Mark, AE, Stroet, M <i>Engineering Transferable Atomic Force Fields: Empirical Optimization of Hydrocarbon Lennard-Jones Interactions by Direct Mapping of Parameter Space.</i> J. Chemical Theory and Computation. In Press</p> <p>Sanzogni, AV, AV, Stroet, M, Sharma, A, Fox, M, Nada, S, Burn, PL, Mark, AE <i>Spontaneous penetration, diffusion and binding of water and oxygen within an amorphous organic light-emitting diode thin film: Implications for the performance and stability of organic semiconductor devices.</i> Advanced Materials, Submitted</p>

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	We have consulted with users of the simulation repository on the development of a new metadata standard in the future as well as improvements to the uploading process.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	We work closely with UNIQUEST on translation. The ATB has been licenced to multiple commercial entities.
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	Users are required to register with the site to submit or download molecule data. Downloads are monitored for each user.

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Grants	The ARC Centre of Excellence in Quantum Biotechnology has been funded which will ensure continued availability of resources to the project.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

The basic model we proposed to incorporate partner data proved very popular. Users both within Australia and across the globe have shown strong interest even in the preliminary stages. The enhancements in the usability of ATB have correlated with a sharp uptick in the numbers of users. Changes in our data structures to accommodate the incorporation of data from partner organizations led to a general streamlining of our own procedures, simplifying ongoing management. The consolidation of data opened avenues we did not anticipate. The strategy of starting with a small consortium of data contributors for the simulation repository allowed us to collect feedback and refine metadata standards in a controlled manner that would not have been possible with either developing it entirely in isolation or opening up the service completely for public uploads at the start of development.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

Governance: Governance was relatively simple given the nature of the project which involved incorporation of partner data into a pre-existing structure as opposed to the co-operative development of a new structure. Developer meetings were held each Thursday with specific people invited based on the current task. This primarily involved researchers at UQ but also researchers at Griffith. We note two of the major contributors to the projects (one based at ANU and one based at UTS) re-located to UQ during the project and thus could directly participate in joint meetings. Thus, it was possible to obtain informal feedback. This development was not anticipated at the start of the project. One aspect that did complicate the formal governance plans was the major data loss and the inability to directly import partner data in the first year. The area where external consensus was most important. The inability to accept new data until the later stages of the project resulted in some loss of momentum.

Risk Management: Two major challenges were encountered the impact of which were not foreseen. One was a major storage failure that occurred in the first year of the project. Storage facilities were not considered a major risk in the project as the data concerned was held on University of Queensland's long-term storage and was fully backed up. What was later discovered was that our allocation had been

part of a pilot program for research data projects and that the hardware and protocols used for the pilot were not compatible with what was eventually rolled out university wide. This severely affected progress for several reasons: a) aspects of the project had to be deferred as we could not operate on the data until the source of the error was traced and the data recovered, b) creating sufficient space on the legacy hardware for a large volume of data to be restored from tape took 4-5 months as our data constituted a significant proportion of the space on the device and we were dependent on external staff to move other data, and c) time was needed to check the recovered data and validate our protocols. In addition, the hardware our data was stored on could not be accessed via certain university facilities (advertised capabilities). This included remote access protocols which would allow external users to upload large datasets without UQ credentials (a key requirement of our project). It took a further 9 months for our data to be migrated to the appropriate physical hardware. These problems were difficult to anticipate because precisely how our data was stored centrally, and its ramifications, were largely hidden.

A second unexpected challenge was related to the CKAN front end used for the simulation repository. Several key plugins (e.g., AAF) had stopped being actively maintained as a new CKAN version had been announced. This left a challenge as to whether to update plugins ourselves and risk code being superseded or wait for the new release and risk delays in the ability to implement features. How our data sets are stored on university facilities and the timing of software releases were both beyond our control. The mitigation strategy implemented is to store raw data obtained from the user independently of processed data used by the frontend, giving the ability to rebuild the system from scratch as needed. This has several advantages. First, it removed dependency on a single interfacing system such as CKAN. Second, it decreased the interdependence between the data structure and the display engine, meaning to add new metadata or move to a new display engine only required modifying the parsers rather than restructuring the data itself. This required more work up front but simplifies later tasks.

As noted above, a number of challenges stemmed from situations in which the claimed capabilities of facilities did not match reality. This included where CKAN plugins no longer worked, where DOIs could not be provided, and where certain data access arrangements were only available on specific hardware or were mutually excluded. These limitations could only have been identified during implementation.

Changes to the project: The key elements of the project remained unchanged throughout. The scheduling and ordering of tasks, however, needed to evolve continuously. The intension had been to focus initially on the collection of user simulation data, then work on metadata generation. The uncertainty regarding our stored data meant instead that for the beginning half of the project we could only operate on internal data as opposed to have partners upload data directly.